

Controversies Surrounding The Legal Status Of Euthanasia: An Absence Of Consensus Between The Proponents And The Opponents

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 17, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 08, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords: Euthanasia, Mercy Killing, Physician-Assisted Suicide, Right To Life, Right To Die</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4519679</p>	<p><i>The Euthanasia debate has, since the time immemorial, been one of the most controversial topics within the international community. The differing opinions centers on two fundamental concepts: the right to life and the right to die. The controversy on this fundamental issue cuts across a wide range of complex and dynamic aspects, such as legal, medical, political, religious, social and ethical aspects of the civilized society. While some European countries might have authorized it in order to alleviate the suffering of people with incurable or debilitating diseases or unbearable suffering with no prospect of improvement, it has been rejected by a large number of countries upholding the sanctity of life. This study, therefore, examines the legal status of Euthanasia or mercy killing in different countries, such as the Netherlands, Germany, France and the United Arab Emirates (U.A.E). The paper also discusses the position of euthanasia in the context of the European Court of Human Rights and International law with a view to articulating legal, political and socio-ethical viewpoints.</i></p>

Introduction

The first two countries to adopt the law authorizing euthanasia in the world are the Netherlands (2001) and Belgium (2002). Several countries are now considering the possibility of adopting such a kind of a law. In all the religions, the right to life is considered as a sacred one, based on the honor and dignity of the human being, and on the principle of the inviolability and preservation of this life from any assault that may thwart it. That is why the killing of oneself is considered as one of the most heinous crimes. In addition to that, the monotheistic religions have agreed that life is a gift from God that no one but God has the right to its disposal. However, a person's life may go through difficult circumstances when he suffers from difficulties or intractable diseases that may either lead him to a state of helplessness or despair to recover due to the excruciating pain that might have accompanied it. This reality is the one that actually led to the issue of euthanasia, and thus, become one of the contentious issues throughout the world, in terms of its legal status and the efforts to justify it morally, religiously and ethically.

Concept of euthanasia

Legal references outline various terms that have been adopted to denote the word: "Euthanasia", such as 'mercy bullet', 'mercy killing', 'murder for compassion or pity', all of which tend to indicate one thing, which is: "the deliberate advancement of a patient's or person's death for the benefit of that patient or person, by means of painless medical methods". In another vein, it is an attempt to put an end to the life of a sick person due to an incurable or debilitating disease. It is also known as the contemporary scientific medical expression facilitating the death of a terminally ill person on the request of the physician handling the patient, or a "medically facilitated death of terminally ill persons. The crux of the matter here is that there is no specific provision for it in most of the legal systems. It is, therefore, usually regarded as either a suicide (if performed by the patient himself) or a murder (if performed by another person).

Historical origination

The word "euthanasia", in the medical profession, was used for the first time in the thirteenth century by an English philosopher Roger Bacon when he says: "Doctors must strive to restore the health to the patients so as relieve them of their pain, but if they discover that there is no hope to restore their health to them, then they must prepare for a mercy killing or for an easy death". Therefore, in my own personal opinion, the physicians involved should not continue to torment their patients despite knowing fully well that there is no hope for the patient to be cured. Instead, it is for them to quench the pain with their hands. In the ancient Greece and Rome, before the advent of Christianity, attitudes toward infanticide, active euthanasia, and suicide were all not considered to be tolerant. According to Michael Manning: "No serious discussion of euthanasia was even possible in the European Christendom until the eighteenth-century". Scholars and authors used to attack the

church's authoritative teaching on all the matters, like the euthanasia for example. However, in 1870, physicians like Samuel Williams began to advocate for the use of anesthetics to relieve the pain of death, and systematically proposed the use of anesthetics and morphine to deliberately end the life of a suffering patient.

Neurotic categories of Euthanasia:

Medical experts are of the view that there are three main categories of a neurotic Euthanasia, and they are as described below:

- (i) The first one being a state of coma in its fourth highest degree. This is a kind of a situation where a patient is placed in a state of artificial respiration due to advanced coma with severe brain damage.
- (ii) The second type is an incurable diseases that causes painful discomfort, such as cancer, especially when it spreads to the whole body.
- (iii) The third one is a kind of a chronic pneumonia that prevents the patient from breathing without the usage of artificial respirational machines. Also, in this category are other difficult and intractable diseases that could not be medically cured.

Types of euthanasia:

Medical anecdote is replete to have several ways by which euthanasia could be applied on a patient. The most important of them are as amply described below:

- **Firstly:** Active or direct killing; such as giving of a lethal dose of a certain drug to the patient purposely to put an end to his life. This could either be in the form of an optional or voluntary state that is based on a previously written testament from the patient, or be in the form of an involuntary case where a physician, on accessing the condition of the patient, is able to simply render the patient unconscious with pain reducing drugs that will allow the patient to die naturally.
- **Secondly:** Assisted suicide; such as firing a gunshot on the head, or leaping onto the ground from a high place.
- **Thirdly:** Indirect killing; that is done by giving certain drug to the patient so as to reduce the patient's pain or state of stress. Thus, over a time, these drugs would have complications, and therefore, inhibits the breathing state of the patient.
- **Fourthly:** Ineffective killing; This is done the action of restraining from treating the patient or withdrawing or withholding the necessary treatment, such as obstructing the vital equipment to maintain life, or stopping the operation of the machine, or reducing the amount of oxygen, or giving the patient, special medicines in stages that may eventually lead to stop the heart from functioning.

Nation's States and Public Legislations: Controversy and Diversity:

An attempt to legalize euthanasia in some countries at the beginning was thorny and difficult, particularly, from the religious and ethical aspects. Although, there are several tough opposing sides against the legalization of euthanasia in many countries. Some of the attempts and advocacy against its legalization resulted in failure due to the impact of religion on the society. The earliest American statute meant to explicitly outlaw an assisted suicide, such as section 20, subsection 4 of Act 19 of the New York Laws was enacted in New York on 10th December, 1828. In view of this development, many of the new States and Territories modelled towards the New York's pattern. In 1854, the Washington's first Territorial Legislature outlawed the assistance of another person to commit self-murder. In 1905-1906, a bill to legalize euthanasia was defeated in the Ohio house of legislation, while in 1906, a similar initiative that would not only legalize euthanasia for terminal adults, but also for 'hideously deformed or daft children' was introduced and defeated as well. The first few countries to authorize mercy killing were the Netherlands in 2001 and Belgium in 2002. However, few years before then, the state of Oregon was the first state in the United States to authorize physician-assisted suicide in 1997. As time goes on, the ambivalent wave arrived in Asia in 2009 when the Supreme Court of South Korea recognized the "**right to die with dignity**" in its decision that warrants the approval of a request made by the family of a brain-dead woman, that the life-support apparatus should be removed from her. In 1935, the Voluntary Euthanasia Legislation Society (VELS) was established in England by C. Kellick Millard who was a retired public health physician. Nebraska Senator, John Comstock proposed a legislation known as the Voluntary Euthanasia Act advocating for the legalization of active euthanasia. Despite the fact that the proposal was not supported by the authorities concerned, it however, interestingly emerged as one of the bold steps taken towards the legalization of euthanasia.

A. Euthanasia in the Netherlands: A Conditional Acceptance

Despite the fact that Article 293 of the amended Dutch penal code criminalized Euthanasia when it states that: "Any person who terminates the life of another person at that other person's express and earnest request, shall be liable to a term of imprisonment not exceeding twelve years or a fine of the fifth category", it is, however, noted that Euthanasia in the Netherlands is regulated by: "Termination of Life on Request and Assisted Suicide Act" which was passed in 2001 and took effect in 2002. The current Dutch legislation only allows the performance of Euthanasia on certain cases, but all in all, euthanasia in form of suggesting or inciting suicide or

assisted suicide are still legally considered as criminal offenses. However, the law contains ‘five liability relief clause’ otherwise known as “due care criteria” which are expected to be strictly followed by the physicians”, and they are as follow:

- (a) The conviction to ensure that the request for euthanasia is voluntarily made by the patient without any persuasion, and should be medically scrutinized before it is considered;
- (b) The conviction to ascertain the persistent suffering of the patient, or a state whereby the patient’s pain becomes unbearable;
- ©The conviction that the patient is informed about the situation he is into, as well as the slim chances to survive;
- (d) The conviction that the patient is aware that there is no any other reasonable medical solution to the situation he is into; and,
- (e) The conviction to ensure that the physician in charge has consulted at least one other independent physician who has seen the patient and gave his opinion in writing, regarding the “due care criteria” referred to in parts a - d.

i. Adolescents and Euthanasia

At this junction, it is pertinent to mention that the law, as operated in the Netherlands, allows adolescents or those who have not yet reach the legal age, the right to resort to euthanasia. This is in accordance with cases that may involve any of the categories of age-bracket of the patient as demonstrated below:

- **Case No. 1: Patient between the ages of 16-18:** If the minor patient has attained an age between sixteen and eighteen, and deemed to have a reasonable understanding of the consequences of his request, the physician may consider the request made by the patient to get his life terminated or to put an end to his life through an assisted suicide, after the parent or an elderly person exercising parental authority and/or his guardian have been involved in the decision process.
- **Case No. 2: Patient between the ages of 12-16:** If the age of the minor patient is between twelve and sixteen, and is considered to have a reasonable understanding of his request, the physician may accept the request of the patient, provided that the parent or the elderly person exercising parental authority and/or his guardian agree to terminate the life of the patient or agree to end the life of the patient through assisted suicide.

The question here now is: ‘what about the children whose ages are less than 12 or those who are between 1 and 12?’. Is this law applicable to them? A closer examination of the aforementioned law, shows that there is no any provision for the categories of children whose ages are less than 12. However, in practice and reality, and based on some official statements from certain quarters in the Netherlands, the impression is that the situation is in favor of this direction. For example, the Dutch government, in October 2020, announced the plans to allow the physicians to put an end to the lives of terminally ill children who are under the age of 13. Also, in a letter to the parliament, the Dutch health minister, Hugo de Jonge proposed that the Law on Euthanasia should be expanded to include the suffering children between the ages of 1 and 12.

B. France’s Continuous Deep Sedation (CDS) :An Alternative to Euthanasia

In France, Euthanasia originally, is illegal. However, the French Law of 2nd February 2016, which gives the terminally ill patients, the right to be put into Continuous Deep Sedation (CDS) was adopted. The CDS is a kind of a practice where a physician uses sedative medication resulting in reduction or elimination of the consciousness of a patient until he/she dies. While some have described this as a “passive euthanasia”, the law, however, draws a distinction between euthanasia and CDS, thereby making France the first country to legislate such a kind of law. According to some of the French physicians, “Deep sedation is not different from euthanasia, because there is no usage of lethal injection”

The CDS law of 2016 was adopted on the bases of two basic conditions that must be met so that the physician concerned would not be subjected to any legal suite. The first condition is that the CDS should be at the request of the patient who may fall within any of the following two circumstances: (i) if a patient is refractory to treatments, by having a serious and incurable condition that is life-threatening within a short term; and, (ii) if a patient with a serious and incurable illness decides to stop receiving treatment due to an unbearable suffering that may likely result in death. The pertinent question here is that: what if the patient is not able to express his/her wishes? The answer to that is not far fetched. If the physician stops the life-sustaining treatment so as to avoid a persistent or unbearable suffering, the physician may implement the CDSUD treatment, unless, the patient in question is able to have earlier advanced his objection to such a kind of an alternative treatment.

C: Euthanasia in Germany: A Sensitive Issue subject to the ruling of the Constitutional Court

In Germany, the issue of euthanasia in particular, is complex and sensitive because of the subsequent Nazi campaign that led to the execution of 300,000 people with mental and physical disabilities. For that reason, there should be no need to exert much effort or commitment to making a research into such a kind of issue in Germany. What could be said of the country is that the German penal code; Article 217 to be specific, explicitly prohibits this practice and impose sanction on any physician who practice it. Thus the article states that “Whoever, with the intention of assisting another person to commit suicide, or provides or procures or arranges the opportunity for that person to do so, and whosoever, his or her actions are intended as a cyclical pursuit to that kind of a practice, shall incur a penalty of imprisonment for a term not exceeding three years or a fine.” Although the text of Article 217 of the German Penal Code is very clear regarding the issue of Euthanasia. However, the German society remains divided over an ideology of whether the general personal right includes ‘the right to die or not’? This controversy came to an end when the Constitutional Court, in 2020, issued a very important verdict relating to article 217 where the constituted judges affirmed ‘the right to die’. In addition to that, the German Federal Constitutional Court, on 26 February 2020, upheld the view that the provision in the German Criminal Code criminalizing commercial assisted suicide is unconstitutional. The Court further added that the general personal right comprises ‘the right to die’, and that includes the freedom to take one’s life, as well as the right to seek and use voluntarily offered help to do so.

D: Euthanasia in the United Arab Emirates and: An Interdiction with Extenuating Excuse

Firstly, there is the need to clarify that though, the fundamental principles of law in the UAE are drawn from the Islamic law. However, most of the legislations are based on the European concepts of Civil law, especially the French legal system. According to the UAE legislation, putting an end to the life of a patient with no hope of recovery from an illness (euthanasia), is considered as premeditated murder, even if it is meant to relieve pain and suffering. In 2008, the UAE adopted the so-called Medical Liability Law (Federal Law No. 10). This law expressly prohibits euthanasia on the basis of Article 9, which, thus, states clearly that: “*A patient’s life may not be terminated for any reason whatsoever, even if it is at his request or that of his guardian or custodian*”. The same law also mentioned the penalty for those people who may violate this provision when it states in Article 30 that: “Without prejudice to the provisions of the Islamic Sharia, anyone who violates article (9) of this Law is liable to a punishment of imprisonment not less than ten years”.

When the government of the United Arab Emirates realized the need to introduce changes to the existing medical law in 2016, it adopted a new law with the aim to regulate medical practice and to harmonize the appropriate areas of concern with regard to medical liability and responsibility. That which is done by taking into account the incessant development in the health care system in the UAE. This new law on Medical Liability, is, therefore, named as the Federal Decree Law No. 4 of 2016. Thus, the law is able to emphasize most of the topical areas that were mentioned in the previous law through the usage of similar phrases and headings, especially in the areas of interdiction of euthanasia and the punishment prescribed. For example it states in Article 10 that: “*The patient’s life may not be terminated for any reason whatsoever, even if it is at his request or the request of his family guardian or legal guardian*”. The law, however, added a new paragraph regarding the removal of resuscitation equipment to article 10 by stating the accurate medical criteria that is required to be fulfilled in paragraph 2 that: “Resuscitation equipment may not be removed unless the heart and respiration stop completely, or when the brain completely stop to function. A decision stating that such a kind of a halt is irreversible could then be reached and issued by the Minister or the physician. The same parity is noted between Article 96 and 97 of the UAE Penal law of 1987 and the Medical Liability Law of 2016. For example, Article 96 used the term: “non-malicious motives” without giving the exact meaning of that phrase. Some scholars, are, however, of the view that the term covers ‘mercy killing’.

A thorough examination of this Article shows that the legal excuse that may be considered during the course of an extenuating and aggravating circumstances is the main issue that was raised in this article. So, therefore, “Extenuating excuses and aggravating circumstances as stated in Article 96 are not referring to anything but the juvenile state of the culprit or the commission of a crime with a non-malicious motive”. Therefore, when a judge is determining a case that is related to Article 96 of the Penal Code, He should try to reduce the punishment of the physician who is found practicing euthanasia, based on the fact that euthanasia is one of the cases that was indirectly raised in Article 96. In addition to that, Article (97) goes further to clarify that: “If an extenuating excuse exists for a crime punishable by death penalty, it shall be commuted to life or temporary imprisonment or to a penalty of detention not less than one year, and if it is a kind that is punishable by imposition of a life or temporary imprisonment, it shall be commuted to a penalty of detention not less than three months, unless the law prescribed otherwise”. There is the need to add at this junction that the Emirati society, being an open one, has accepted the idea to render the help that is needed by a terminally ill person to die. This is shown in a study that is conducted by Tawam Hospital on the opinion of the community and patients regarding the issue of euthanasia. The study, in its findings, showed that nearly half of the 226 people who participated in the survey

that was carried out by the Hospital, approved that the controversial euthanasia should be performed on terminally ill patients, while about 50 per cent of the relatives of the terminally ill patients accept the idea as well.

Universal Declaration of Human Rights and Euthanasia: An Inherent Right to Life

Although the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) of 1948 is not a binding one. However, it is considered as one of the most important historical documents and declarations known to the international community since it was drafted by representatives and members from diverse legal and cultural backgrounds from all over the world. This declaration, which contains more than 30 legal provisions, deals with sundry rights of human being of which one of them is the right to life. No doubt, euthanasia, regardless of its diversification, represents a violation of international law and exposes the citizenry in general to an unreasonable risk of their right to life. That is the same general understanding inferred from a research that was carried out by John Fleming on euthanasia titled: "Euthanasia: Human Rights and Inalienability". Article 3 of the declaration, explicitly, indicates that the right to life is not important by a mere saying that "Everyone has the right to life, liberty and security of person". Therefore, if some people consider that removing of life support devices or turning off devices on a terminally ill patient as an inhuman treatment, then Article 5 from the same declaration considered the factual legal instance that "No one shall be subjected to torture or to cruel or inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment". In view of that, some legal jurists maintain that to put an end to the life of a patient on the desire of the family of the patient is a direct violation of an important principle of law which is the principle of 'equality before the law', as emphasized in article 7 of the UDHR that states: "All are equal before the law and are entitled without any discrimination to equal protection of the law". The same right to life is reiterated in another important treaty which is known as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1996, as evident in its Article 6 that: "Every human being has the inherent right to life. The right shall be protected by the law. No one shall be arbitrarily deprived of his life".

At this juncture, it is necessary to point out that after several years of the adoption of Universal Declaration of Human Rights in 1952, voices have been raised in the West calling for an amendment to the Universal Declaration to authorize the euthanasia. For example, the British and American Euthanasia Societies submitted a request to the United Nations Commission on Human Rights to modify the United Nations Declaration of Human Rights to include 'the right to die' or 'the right to euthanasia' or 'merciful death' for people with debilitating and incurable illness. At long run, those proposals and initiatives calling for such an amendment could not see the light of the day.

European Court of Human Rights: Unavailability of Common Law Provision for 'the right to assisted suicide'

Up till today, euthanasia continues to be a hotly debated topic in healthcare and legal fields, even within a country, such as what is happening in the United States. It is tolerated in some states, while it is rejected in others, because of the fact that it is considered as a crime of murder. This controversy cuts across complex aspects of legal and ethical points of view. The writer is, therefore, of the opinion that it is necessary, at this juncture, to take an insight into controversy surrounding the issue at the platform of the judiciary at international level. Specifically, the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) has, since, been dealing with numerous cases on euthanasia. However, all the cases so far dealt with by the ECHR centered on two main provisions, which are the Articles 2 and 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights.

The first case to be highlighted occurred in the United Kingdom (UK), in *Pretty v. the United Kingdom* on 29th April, 2002. In this case, the applicant was battling for her life due to the effect of the motor neurone disease. This disease eventually led the applicant paralyzed from the neck downwards. While the chances to survive are very slim, her intellect and capacity to make decisions are unimpaired. However, based on the fact that the final stages of the disease are distressing and stressful, she then decided to control how and when she would like to die, and for the fact that she could not commit suicide alone, she requested her husband to help her. Although, to commit suicide in English law, is not regarded as a crime, whereas physician-assisted suicide is a grievous offence punishable by law. All what she wants, therefore, is to ensure that her husband would be free from being prosecuted in case he decides to assist her. On seeing that the authorities turned down her request, she decided to complain that how on earth could her husband not be able to free from being prosecuted after he might have assisted her to die? Such a kind of request infringes the provisions of Article 2 (right to life), Article 3 (prohibition of torture and degrading treatment), Article 9 (freedom of thought, conscience and religion) and Article 14 (non-discrimination) of the ECHR. The Court, in the case of *Pretty v. the United Kingdom* 2002, upheld the view that the provision of Article 2 of the ECHR on the 'right to life' is not violated, and therefore submits that the right to life could not, without a distortion of language, be absolutely interpreted or construed as a right to die. The Court also believed that there had been no violation of Article 3 of the Convention regarding the prohibition of inhuman or degrading treatment, or Article 8 (right to respect for private life), or Article 9 (freedom of conscience), or Article 14 (prohibition of discrimination), even though the applicant continues to suffer from depression, distress and pain because she was not allowed to have access to assisted

suicide. The State, however, has the right to bar any other action that may, ordinarily, lead to termination of human life.

Another prominent case to be examined on the issue of Euthanasia is the one that occurred in France; a country that is yet to authorize euthanasia or assisted suicide. In the famous case of Vincent Lambert v. France, the applicants are the parents, half-brother and sister of Vincent Lambert who, in 2008, sustained a head injury in a road-traffic accident resulting in tetraplegia. Legal battles in French and European courts, over years, pitched a tent with Lambert's Catholic parents and two of his siblings – who want to keep him alive – against his wife and other brothers and sisters who believe the most humane option is to let him die. They complained in particular about the judgment delivered on 24 June 2014 by the French *Conseil d'État* which, on relying on, and among other things, the medical report submitted by a panel of three doctors, declaring that the decision taken by the physician that is taking care of Vincent Lambert on 11 January, 2014 to discontinue his artificial nutrition and hydration is lawful. The applicants complained that such a kind of a decision contradicts the obligation of the State as declared in Article 2 of the European Convention on Human Rights, as regards 'the right to life'. By the majority votes of twelve to five, the Grand Chamber upheld the view that a State may, however, simply rendered a patient unconscious with pain reducing drugs and eventually allow the patient to die. The Court further emphasized that it is the primary duty of the domestic authorities to verify whether the decision to withhold treatment or supportive measures is compatible with the domestic legislation and the Convention, and to establish the wishes of the patient in accordance with the national law. The European Court of Human Rights in its verdict, finally clarifies that withdrawal of artificial nutrition and hydration from Vincent Lambert was consistent with French domestic law and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms. Few years later the same court looked into another case involving Afiri and Biddarri v. France, 2018. That case was about the withdrawal of treatments from a 14 year old girl who was in a permanent vegetative state after a cardiac arrest caused by an autoimmune disease. Her parents; Mrs. Afiri and Mr. Biddarri persistently opposed the physicians' proposal to withhold the treatments of their daughter, after having fulfilled the conditions and procedures prescribed by the French law.

Conclusion

In the foregoing analyses, it is demonstrated that the debate on euthanasia still remains a matter of contentious within the medical, legal and human rights perspectives. We have been able to argue this complex and dynamic issue from the standpoints of both the opponents and the supporters with a view to exploring the role of such practices in the contemporary healthcare system, and also attempted, on the other hand, to present the plight of the sufferers and the physicians involved. The divergent opinions on the matter, centers on two fundamental concepts: the right to life and the right to die. In the context of our analyses on the status of euthanasia at the international level, it is established that, in general, the final synthesis are dominated by those who are opposed to its legalization. We, however discovered that the viewpoints of the international community on euthanasia continue to change from time to time. While countries like the Netherlands, France, Germany and the UAE have changed or are trying to reconsider their directions over the years, others have either reduced their restrictions on euthanasia or issued laws that legalize it under certain conditions after it been previously prohibited.

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